

GENERAL AWARENESS TOWARDS ENVIRONMENTAL CONCERNS – A SURVEY

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Abstract

"Nature provides a free lunch, but only if we control our appetites."

—William Ruckelshaus

The word "Environment" is most commonly used to describe "natural" environment and means the sum of all living and non-living things that surround an organism, or group of organisms. Environment includes all elements, factors, and conditions that have some impact on growth and development of certain organism. The environmental issues in India become more serious every day and she is turning into a bit of a mess on this front but with a serious lack of education and over 1 Billion people, a huge amount of which are in dire poverty, it's hardly surprising. The recent boom in its industries, little or no environmental education, infrastructure nearly at bursting point not to mention the huge deforestation that's going on. In fact, there is no shortage at all of government legislation protecting the environment but unfortunately it is never enforced due to flagrant abuse of power, corruption and lack of resources. The aim of the research was to check the general awareness of citizens towards environmental concerns. Structured questionnaire in the form of google form was used in the study. The participants of the study included 8 males and 52 females each of different age group and from various educational backgrounds. It was found that every participant involved in the study was equally concerned about the environment and the damage we as humans are making to it.

Introduction

In recent decades, many environmental problems have increased as the result of human

activities and unplanned management of the technological development those interference ecosystems. Therefore, a dispute between the importance of conservation and preservation of ecosystems to protect environment and the necessity to satisfy human desire by sacrifice the environment has been arise across the world. According to Glossary of Environment Statistics the term “environmental protection” can be defined as the prevention to conserve and preserve the standard healthy level of environmental media by reducing the production of pollutants or polluting substances in environmental media (1997, internet). Various human activities have induce many undesirable effects to the environment which can be threatening human health, economic, natural resources and gene pool of ecosystems such as pollutions, greenhouse effect, global warming and soil erosion. This research article is mainly focusing on the worth to fight for protecting the environment for several reasons. Firstly, the environmental pollution is one of the main reasons why we should fight to protect environment. Besides, global warming is also another reason caused by the deforestation. Furthermore, warm climate change and flood also increase the opportunity of spread out pests and vector diseases.

Need of the study

The effect that humanity is having on the environment is becoming ever-more important. Through our actions we are destroying habitats and endangering the lives of future generations. At this point there is no denying the fact that our environment is changing. Hundreds of studies have been conducted to demonstrate that this is happening and it is having an effect on life around us. The need of protecting the environment especially in today’s time has become a basic living need. Today, when we look at our surroundings, what we see is buildings, cars, multiplexes etc. The human needs are limitless and when it comes to urbanisation, they are never satisfied. We as humans compromise the nature according to our convenience. But, we often forget about the role that the environment plays in our lives. The green environment that we live in consists of air, water, sunlight, trees etc. Everything that the environment consists of is important to us. The humans have become the inhabitants of two worlds. The first is the one which is natural i.e. it contains trees, water, animals, soil etc. and the second one is the man-made world which includes

urbanisation, social institutions, social media etc. Using secondary research, this paper suggests how aware the citizens of different age groups, gender and with varied educational qualification are towards the changing environmental conditions. The research paper checks their sensitivity towards the environment concerns.

AIM OF THE STUDY

The following was the broad aim of the study:

1. To study general awareness towards environmental concerns.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study general awareness towards environmental concerns.
2. To compare general awareness towards environmental concerns on the basis of age, gender and Qualifications.

Hypothesis (Null Hypothesis):

The following null hypotheses have been formulated for the study:

1. There is no significant difference towards environmental concerns on the basis of age.
2. There is no significant difference towards environmental concerns on the basis of Gender.
3. There is no significant difference towards environmental concerns on the basis of qualification.

METHODOLOGY

In the present study, an attempt has been made to investigate the general awareness of people towards environmental concerns. In order to achieve the pre-determined objectives of the study, the researcher has planned the entire process of the work in terms of research design.

DESIGN OF THE STUDY

A survey type study was designed to find out significant differences based on age, gender and qualification to check the general awareness towards the environment.

SAMPLE

For the purpose of the study, a general survey was conducted which included 60 people

from around Mumbai, Navi Mumbai and Thane areas as the sample was collected using online mode through Google forms which included people from various age groups and diverse educational background.

TESTS USED AND THEIR DESCRIPTION

The researcher used questionnaire made by her through online mode.

PROCEDURE OF DATA COLLECTION

The researcher made a Google form for the purpose of data collection. The link for the Google form was sent on email to the participants explaining the importance of the study. The participants filled the online forms and their responses were recorded for further analysis.

TECHNIQUES OF DATA ANALYSIS

The present research used statistical techniques of ANOVA and t-test. One-way analysis of variance was applied to find out the significance of mean difference among the participants of different age group and various educational backgrounds. T-test was applied to find out the significance of mean difference between the genders.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

Testing Hypothesis 1

1. The null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference towards environmental concerns on the basis of age.

Table 1: Mean Scores on the basis of age

Age Group	Mean
18-25	30.62
26-35	30
36-50	33

The technique used to test this hypothesis was the One-Way ANOVA. The following table shows the relevant statistics of the scores on the basis of age.

Table 2: ANOVA scores on the basis of age

Source	SS	df	MS	F	P
Treatment (between groups)	22.8481	2	11.424	0.58	0.565341
Error	664.8276	34	19.5538		
Total	687.6757	36			

The preceding table shows the F-ratio is not significant ($P = 0.565341$). Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Thus, it could be concluded that there is no significant difference amongst the participants of different age group towards various environmental concerns.

Fig 1

2. There is no significant difference towards environmental concerns on the basis of Gender.

The technique used to test this hypothesis was the t-test. The following table shows the relevant statistics of the scores on the basis of age.

Table 3: Mean t-test scores on the basis of gender

Groups	N	d-f	Mean	Standard Division	t-ratio	Table Value		Significance level
						0.05	0.01	
Female	52	58	30.33	2.12	0.26	1.97	2.59	NS
Male	8		32.5	5.66				

From the table it can be seen that the obtained t- ratio is less than the tabulated t value. Thus 't' is not significant. Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference towards environmental concerns on the basis of Gender.

Fig 2

3. There is no significant difference towards environmental concerns on the basis of qualification.

Table 4: Mean Scores on the basis of qualification

Qualification	Mean
Graduate	30.18
Post Graduate	31.6
Others	30.2

The technique used to test this hypothesis was the One-Way ANOVA. The following table shows the relevant statistics of the scores on the basis of qualification.

Table 5: ANOVA scores on the basis of qualification

Source	SS	df	MS	F	P
Treatment (between groups)	23.3232	2	11.6616	0.6	0.552429
Error	1042.1856	54	19.2997		
Total	1065.5088	56			

The preceding table shows the F-ratio is not significant ($P = 0.552429$). Hence the null hypothesis is accepted.

Thus, it could be concluded that there is no significant difference amongst the participants from various educational backgrounds towards various environmental concerns.

Fig 3

Conclusion:

In conclusion, we can say that there are several factors which contribute towards environmental destruction. Acid rain which is formed due to carbon dioxide, other reasons could be global warming caused by the deforestation which increases the global temperature caused the occurrence of ice melting. Moreover, the global warming change

the climate become warmer and flood encouraged the growth of the pests and vectors like malaria and dengue fever to spread the disease out to the environment which increases the level of biochemical oxygen demand. Therefore, the environment should be protected for a better life in future. This research paper was just an attempt to check the awareness of people towards the environment. Pressures on the environment will continue to increase as a result of human activities across the globe. Such research papers are indicators that we need to progress towards a sustainable society and it also proves valuable and alarming to respond and prevent many environmental problems.

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